

Comparative Study of Nonlinear Optical Properties of Benzylidene Aniline Derivatives

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Abstract

Nonlinear optical materials have recently attracted much attention because of their potential applications in emerging technologies like signal transmission, data storage, optical switching, laser printing, displays, photolithography, remote sensing, chemical and biological species detection, high resolution spectroscopy, medical diagnosis and under water monitoring and communication. Some polar organic crystals, which form a non-centrosymmetric structure exhibit second-order nonlinear optical properties that far surpassed those of the conventional materials has led to the synthesis and evaluation of a wide range of potentially useful solids materials showing high optical non linearity. Research has shown that the second-order nonlinear optical properties of organic crystal materials are closely related to their molecular structures. Among many organic compounds the second harmonic generations of Benzylidene aniline derivates are noticeable materials for the excellent green light transmittance and good crystal stability. In the present work a comparative study of 4-chloro 4'-methyl benzylidene aniline and 4-bromo 4'-methyl benzylidene aniline nonlinear optical single crystals are reported. The details of the experiment and the results will be discussed in detail.

Keywords: Benzylidene aniline, Organic Crystal, Second Harmonic Generation, Stability.

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